

Appendix A. Four-part questionnaire evaluating quality of life impact and risk factors in Iraqi medical students with chronic rhinosinusitis.

SECTION 1: Socio-Demographic Data

1. Age:
2. Gender: Male Female
3. Nationality: Iraqi Non-Iraqi
4. City of residence:
5. Region of residence: Baghdad Southern region Northern region Western region
6. Nature of residence: Urban Rural
7. Education level: High school or less College Postgraduate
8. Occupation: Student Employed Unemployed Housewife
9. Marital Status: Single In relationship
10. Type of residence: Apartment Villa Other

SECTION 2: Risk Factors

11. Do you smoke? Yes No
12. Are you frequently exposed to cleaning chemicals/detergents? Yes No
13. Are you regularly exposed to dirt, plants, or dust? Yes No
14. Do you have pets at home? Yes No
15. Do you suffer from any of these chronic comorbidities? (Select all that apply)
 Asthma Seasonal allergy Non-seasonal allergy Nasal septal deviation
 Gastrointestinal disorders Depression Eczema Immune disorders None
16. Do you have a family history of any of the following? (Select all that apply)
 Asthma Allergies Sinusitis Eczema None

SECTION 3: SNOT-22 Questionnaire

Please rate the severity of the following problems over the past 2 weeks using the scale below:

- 0 = No problem
- 1 = Very mild problem
- 2 = Mild or slight problem
- 3 = Moderate problem
- 4 = Severe problem
- 5 = Problem as bad as it can be

1. Need to blow nose 0 1 2 3 4 5
2. Nasal blockage 0 1 2 3 4 5
3. Sneezing 0 1 2 3 4 5
4. Runny nose 0 1 2 3 4 5
5. Cough 0 1 2 3 4 5
6. Post-nasal discharge 0 1 2 3 4 5
7. Thick nasal discharge 0 1 2 3 4 5
8. Ear fullness 0 1 2 3 4 5

9. Dizziness 0 1 2 3 4 5
10. Ear pain 0 1 2 3 4 5
11. Facial pain/pressure 0 1 2 3 4 5
12. Difficulty falling asleep 0 1 2 3 4 5
13. Waking up at night 0 1 2 3 4 5
14. Lack of good night's sleep 0 1 2 3 4 5
15. Waking up tired 0 1 2 3 4 5
16. Fatigue 0 1 2 3 4 5
17. Reduced productivity 0 1 2 3 4 5
18. Reduced concentration 0 1 2 3 4 5
19. Frustrated/Restless/Irritable 0 1 2 3 4 5
20. Sad 0 1 2 3 4 5
21. Embarrassed 0 1 2 3 4 5
22. Sense of smell/taste loss 0 1 2 3 4 5

SECTION 4: Seasonality and Treatment

1. Do your chronic rhinosinusitis symptoms follow a seasonal pattern? Yes No
2. If yes, during which months do your symptoms typically occur (or worsen)?
 Winter Spring Summer Autumn
3. Do you receive any medical treatment for chronic rhinosinusitis? Yes No
4. If yes, which of the following best describes your treatment?
 Self-management Family management Physician prescription
5. Which of the following treatments do you use?
 Nasal saline rinses Antihistamines Antibiotics Corticosteroids Others
6. Do you follow your treatment as prescribed? Yes No
7. Has your condition improved with treatment? Yes No
8. Have you ever undergone sinus surgery? Yes No